

APPLICATIONS OF 3D MATRICES

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Abstract. Three-dimensional matrices, commonly referred to as 3D matrices (and also as tensor-matrices) are mathematical structures that extend the concept of two-dimensional matrices (rows and columns) to three dimensions. With their help, we learn the properties of algebra.

Key words. *Matrices, 3-dimensional algebra, structure constants, multiplication table.*

Thus, a 3D matrix consists of elements arranged in a three-dimensional grid, with each element identifiable using three indices. The dimensions of a 3D matrix are typically described as $n \times m \times p$; where n represents the number of rows (height), m the number of columns (width), and p the number of layers (depth).

The focus here is on cubic matrices (i.e., 3D matrices with dimensions $n \times n \times n$). This preference is due to the fact that such matrices can be viewed as a family of time-dependent (non-associative) algebras, enabling the application of Spectral Theory tools in our study.

Thus, a 3D matrix M of dimension $n \times m \times p$ is uniquely determined by p 2D matrices, M_1, \dots, M_p ; each of dimension $n \times m$, where $M_k := (\omega_{ijk})_{ij}$ where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Definition 1. *A cubic matrix of dimension n is 3D matrix of dimension $n \times n \times n$. The set of all n -dimensional cubic matrices is denoted by C_n .*

From now on we will deal with cubic matrices of dimension n . This focus is chosen because, when considering an n -dimensional linear space A and fixing a base $B = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$, each 3D matrix determines a multiplication in A , thereby endowing A with the structure of an algebra (whether associative or not).

Now we recall the known concept of algebra. Let F be a field and A be a vector space defined over this field and define a binary operation from $A \times A$ to A , and denoted by \cdot ($x \cdot y$ is an element of A that is called the product of x and y). Then A is an algebra over F if the following identities hold for all elements $x, y, z \in A$, and all scalars a and $b \in F$:

- $(x + y) \cdot z = x \cdot z + y \cdot z$;
- $z \cdot (x + y) = z \cdot x + z \cdot y$;
- $(ax) \cdot (by) = (ab)(x \cdot y)$.

For algebras over a field, we recall that a multiplication in A is a bilinear map from $A \times A$ to A and it is completely determined by the multiplication of the basis elements of A .

It's important to note that the associative property is not required in this notion so that the algebra A does not need to be associative. Given a field F , any finite-dimensional algebra can be specified up to isomorphism by giving its dimension (say n), and specifying n^3 structure constants ω_{ijk} , which are scalars. These structure constants determine the multiplication in A via the following rule:

$$e_i \cdot e_j = \sum_{k=1}^n \omega_{ijk} e_k$$

where e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n are basis elements of A . Thus the multiplication of a finite-dimensional algebra is given by a 3D matrix $(\omega_{ijk})_{i,j,k=1}^n$ and this matrix is called the matrix of structure constants.

If we take for every $k = 1, \dots, n$ the matrix

$$M_k = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_{11k} & \dots & \omega_{1nk} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \omega_{n1k} & \dots & \omega_{nnk} \end{pmatrix},$$

then we can write the matrix of structure constants as $M = (M_1 | \dots | M_n)$

Conversely, every 3D matrix $M = (M_1 | \dots | M_n)$ defines a product in A by means the equations $e_i \cdot e_j := \sum_{k=1}^n \pi_k(e_i, e_j) e_k$ where $\pi_k(e_i, e_j)$ denotes the ij -th entry in M_k .

We conclude in this way that fixed a n -dimensional linear space A and a basis $B = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ every multiplication in A is one to one determined a matrix in C_n and vice versa.

we will consider the following multiplication (the reader is invited to consider any other): If $A = (a_{ijk})$ and $B = (b_{ijk})$; where $i, j, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ then

$$A * B = C = (\omega_{ijk})_{i,j,r=1}^n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{ijk} b_{kjr} ,$$

Following [1, 2, 3, 4] recall a notion of cubic matrix and different associative multiplication rules of cubic matrices: a cubic matrix $Q = (q_{ijk})_{i,j,k=1}^n$ is a n^3 -dimensional vector which can be uniquely written as

$$Q = \sum_{k=1}^n q_{ijk} E_{ijk}$$

where E_{ijk} denotes the cubic unit (basis) matrix, i.e. E_{ijk} is a n^3 -cubic matrix whose (i, j, k) th entry is equal to 1 and all other entries are equal to 0.

For any matrices $A = (a_{ijk}), B = (b_{ijk}) \in C_n, \lambda \in F$ we have

$$A + B := (a_{ijk} + b_{ijk}), \lambda A := (\lambda a_{ijk}).$$

We define the following multiplications for basis matrices E_{ijk} :

$$E_{ijk} * E_{lmr} = \sigma_{kl} E_{ia(j,m)r} ,$$

where $a: I \times I \rightarrow I, (j, m) \rightarrow a(j, m) \in I, I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, is an arbitrary associative binary operation and σ_{kl} is the Kronecker symbol.

$$M = \left(\begin{array}{ccc|ccc|ccc} \omega_{111} & \omega_{121} & \omega_{131} & \omega_{112} & \omega_{122} & \omega_{132} & \omega_{113} & \omega_{123} & \omega_{133} \\ \omega_{211} & \omega_{221} & \omega_{231} & \omega_{212} & \omega_{222} & \omega_{232} & \omega_{213} & \omega_{223} & \omega_{233} \\ \omega_{311} & \omega_{321} & \omega_{331} & \omega_{312} & \omega_{322} & \omega_{332} & \omega_{313} & \omega_{323} & \omega_{333} \end{array} \right) \quad (1)$$

Theorem 1. Let A_M be the algebra associated to the matrix $M = (M_1|M_2|M_3)$, given in (1), respect to the basis $B = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$. Then A_M is associative if and only if the following equalities are satisfied, for $i, j = 1, 2, 3$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \omega_{1i1} & \omega_{1i2} & \omega_{1i3} \\ \omega_{2i1} & \omega_{2i2} & \omega_{2i3} \\ \omega_{3i1} & \omega_{3i2} & \omega_{3i3} \end{pmatrix} M_j = M_j \begin{pmatrix} \omega_{i11} & \omega_{i21} & \omega_{i31} \\ \omega_{i12} & \omega_{i22} & \omega_{i32} \\ \omega_{i13} & \omega_{i23} & \omega_{i33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

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